

WOMEN MARKETERS: INCLUSIVENESS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR CAREER GROWTH AND ADVANCEMENT

HEMANTH KUMAR. S¹, SAHANA MADAN² & DITTAKAVI RAMYA SRI³

¹Associate Professor, CMS Business School, Jain University Bangalore, Karnataka, India

²Associate Professor, CMS Business School, Jain University Bangalore, Karnataka, India

³Lecturer, East Point PU College, Kalyanagar, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

ABSTRACT

Indian women span generations and today they play equal participants in every field. Breaking the chains of restraint, women have become ever-motivated and inspired and are riding on the wave of success. The discourses on women's empowerment have increased in general and become more widespread. Women have revolutionised the existing corporate ecosystem. This paper focuses on the perceptions of the Indians on women marketers and their capabilities and potentialities like skill set, socio-cultural barriers, work-life balance and competency. The primary objective of the paper is to understand the association of various dimensions pertaining to the acceptance of women marketers in their career growth and build a relationship between the acceptance of women marketers across dimensions of skill set, socio-cultural barriers, work-life balance and competency. Statistical tool used is SPSS 21 and Chi-Square, Correlation test and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Test (KMO) was conducted to test the hypothesis. The study findings revealed that there is an association between the dimensions of acceptance and the career opportunities provided to the women marketers.

Keywords: Women Empowerment, Marketing Roles, skill Sets, Competency & Work Life

Received: Jul 11, 2018; **Accepted:** Jul 31, 2018; **Published:** Sep 19, 2018; **Paper Id.:** IJMPERDSPL2018102

INTRODUCTION

Gender refers to the socially constructed roles, behaviours, activities and attributes that a given society considers appropriate for men and women (WHO report, 2012).

With a decline in their status from the ancient to medieval times, to the promotion of equal rights by many reformers, the history of women in India has been eventful (Jayapalan 2001). Women in India now participate fully in areas such as education, sports, politics, media, art and culture, service sectors, science and technology, etc. (NRCW, 2006).

Earlier, men were assumed to be more capable and successful than women in all the sectors. Today we are witnessing a trend of a growing brigade of women marketing officers. Women managers and leaders are in huge demand in marketing, media and advertising departments, giving their ability to multitask and their understanding of the core consumers. When dealing with women as a consumer, most marketers think it is wise to have women leaders to frame the product strategies. We see this new trend plays out and as an indication of robust participation of women in the marketing area and the corporate world.

Progression of Women in the Men Driven Society

The world was male-driven in the past (Makova, K. D., & Li, W. H, 2002). Only men were the bread winners of the family and treated as the head of the family (Lim, I. S., 1997). Women were expected to be at home and support the family in their daily routines without giving any suggestions regards to the outside world and work life (Thompson, L., & Walker, A. J., 1989). Many women were not allowed to take independent decisions with respect to their career. Women's freedom of expression was curtailed and in most cases, they ended up being silent spectators (MacKinnon, C. A.1987). But Socio-Economic and Legal changes have increased the participation of women in the labour force is posing a number of challenges.

Among many challenges, managing work and family responsibilities are one of the most significant challenges that women face (Frone et al., 1992; Guendouzi, 2006; Noor, 2004 ;). In an effort to increase work-life balance, women have started entering self-employment to gain more flexibility and control over their Work and personal lives (Baber and Monaghan, 1988; Machung, 1989; ard, 2007). Women employment has recently gained much attention from the perspective of career advancement. This is only natural in view of the fact that an increasing number of women are in the workforce, but only a very small percentage hold top level positions in business and public administration (Alvesson & Billing, 2010).

Shelton, (2006) and Welter, (2004) have stated that this huge transformation led to a major change creating a Women Empowerment era. Today, Developed and under developing countries are promoting women empowerment and its related programmes. The women Leadership programme is one among them to encourage women and boost their self-confidence (Kabeer, N.2005). Companies started believing that women are the ones who can handle crucial positions in a better way (Helgesen, S. 1995). Many Indian companies are hiring well qualified women for various roles in the marketing segment. Women accepted the roles challenging the notion: men perform better and showed remarkable growth over the years (Ragins, B. R., Townsend, B., & Mattis, M. 1998). Women started climbing the ladder of Success overcoming the hindrances placed in their way. Today, there are many role models to inspire the women workforce namely Chitra Ramakrishna, (MD, CEO) National Stock Exchange, Aarthi Subramanian (Executive Director) TCS, Arundhati Bhattacharya (Chairman) State Bank of India, Nita Ambani (Chairperson and Founder) Reliance Foundation and (Non-Executive Director) Reliance Industries. Recently Malini Agarwal (Founder and Creative Director) Miss. Malini Agarwal makes it to the top position of Impact's 50 most influential women in Indian Media, Marketing and Advertising list 2017 followed by Tanya Dubash (Executive Director and Chief Brand Officer) Godrej Group in the second position. The majority of the companies started welcoming women with open hands and became part of their success. Not only in the urban areas, had women in the rural areas also showed fruitful results. They started small scale businesses and are self-employed that became a living example of many such as Ela Bhatt (Founder) Self-Employed Women Association in Bihar.

Not only in the top level of management, had women flourished at various levels of management setting a trend in the society. Administrators or Clerical Levels are generally attractive for women. Some of the reasons are secured family life, work stability and working environment, facilities like transportation, attractive salary, etc. Few women have the clerical working mind-set that gave a perception that all women have the same clerical mind-set. This leads to criticism of women working in the marketing sector; they are not ambitious and innovative compared to men and are not heavy risk takers. At times, women fought battles to get equivalent rights and openings, and expected to be judged on their capacity, competency level rather than on gender. Today the same perception was proved wrong with women leading in the

marketing sector too. Women in the country are reaching heights by grabbing various opportunities in the marketing sector offering to them and becoming a successful story where recognition and responsibilities are at their doorstep. The decisions approved by them are creating waves indirectly in the Indian economy. It is evident that Women Leadership, a part of women empowerment led to a revolution in all the sectors especially in the corporate sector. Numbers are equalising with respect to men and women in various critical positions like Pilot, Politician, Mechanic, Entrepreneur, etc. But even today, few women at a critical situation personally are in a dilemma whether to choose career over personal life or vice-versa. Women always strive hard to maintain work-life balance throughout her career, which is overlooked by few companies. This is one of the hindrance and few companies takes it as a reason for not to promote them to a higher level of authority. Weak portrayal of women in Entrepreneurial positions and the outcomes result in seedling the gender inequality in women and men at times.

Background of the Research and Research Gap

The past research focused on Indians perception on women marketers was very limited and thus arised a need for us to add more information and explore on the untouched areas. The study helped us to gain deeper insights on the Indian perception about women in the field of marketing and how they are embraced in the corporate world. Although there are changes in the Indian mind-set, social taboos and restrictions still exists and women are experiencing burden in balancing their personal and work-life.

This paper focuses on women marketers of the Bangalore city and examines the facts like gender equality and rights in terms of opportunities provided by the companies for women and primarily focuses on how Indians accept women marketers, whether they encourage or discourage them in the field of marketing. The paper also aims to examine whether there is any relationship between a woman's skillset and abilities. Women Empowerment really gave a kick start to women's career in the recent years.

Women Marketers and the Changing Marketing Environment

The marketing environment represents a mix between the internal and external forces which surround an organization and have an impact upon it, especially their ability to build and maintain successful relationships with target customers. Increasing awareness on the various marketing problems has led a shift in the way the consumers go about their life. There has been a change in the consumer's attitude towards a lifestyle. Mitchell, Alan (2008) discussed about the opportunities for women marketers and their capacity to exhibit skills in his research paper. He tried to find whether marketing field is a woman friendly or not. Also, he discussed why there are only a few women at the top of the management hierarchy. He examined the various leader perspectives regarding this topic and speaks about the ways the women marketers should take to mend themselves to fit in this world and feel comfortable. He concludes his paper by stating how the next generation will bring a striking difference by having equally skilled women marketers. Further Harriet Marsh (2000) writes about how gender is an issue in the marketing field. He wrote, only few companies have an equal opportunity to men and women in the top-level management. He found that it takes at least five years of experience for a woman employee to reach top-level management and concludes by stating that, around 42% of women marketers compared to others. Ahlawat S (2004) speaks about the qualitative method that explains about the preferences of Indians over salesmen and sales women and their perspective on their managers in the marketing field. His research primarily focuses on the views of sale person (both men and women) on their supervisor. His study highlights the fact about the target group and explains how important it is to have equal rights for men and women in the marketing world. The group

was done according to the education, gender and age. Another study conducted by Phillips, Judy (2008) administered through the research findings in her paper that the major women business owners are few compared to men. She states that the financial institutions in the United States have compressed growth of a woman in the business. She compares the current situation in U.S with the past situation. It has been observed in the past that women had problem in getting loan for their businesses but the current situation has changed. Legal and Social changes aided women a lot and led to Women Empowerment.

Basil Alzougool, Khadiga Elbargathi, Hiba Habib, Basma Khalaf and Dima Al-Qutub (2015) spoke about the related studies referring to women leadership styles in private sectors in Jordan. Their aim was to find various leadership styles of women entrepreneurs in private and public sector in Jordan and to check if there is any difference between the leadership style among men and women. They found that there was a vast difference in their leadership style, one was transformational and the other was passive avoider. They concluded their research by giving a few recommendations on how to improve power of Women Leadership.

The above research papers are an overview and how women marketers are getting affected in the marketing and corporate field. But none of these cover the perception of Indians on women marketing personnel. Since India is a developing country, it will take time to conduct survey and find suggestions and analyse the perceptions in the right way.

Women tended to rate most of the marketing criteria as having a higher level of importance than men. Women needed more communal support while making decision making of selection of engineering education (Mahajan and Golahit, 2017). Further the study has highlighted women's perceptions and experiences on accessing engineering education through institute's Marketing Mix strategies which enables women to take up strategic position to enjoy success in engineering education and career. Findings of this study revealed that women students in the engineering are better satisfied and act of referring services / programme to others is higher than men students in terms of numbers for a particular set of marketing mix applied to gender. Therefore, it becomes imperative for us to study these dimensions of women marketers.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

PROBLEM STATEMENT, SCOPE, OBJECTIVES AND HYPOTHESIS

Problem Statement

Recent Studies have shown that women are not treated equal with men in various organizations and businesses. Even today many companies advertise the posts exclusively for male applicants assuming that women are not capable of handling that position effectively and efficiently. This paper focuses on whether women are given equal career

opportunities based on their skillset and competency or biased on gender basis in the marketing areas and jobs. Also, the focus is on to find out really men and women have equal rights and respect in the corporate world and how women are able to balance work life.

Scope

The study is specific to the geographical region of Bangalore. This study determines how the women marketers are viewed today. We tried to ascertain a relationship on how Indians view their women marketers and the skillsets, work-life balance etc. We analysed, if these factors have any impact on the acceptance of women marketers in the Indian society.

Objectives

- To study the relationship between the acceptance of women marketers across the dimension of skillset, socio-cultural barriers, work-life balance and competency
- To understand the association of the various dimensions pertaining to the acceptance of women marketers in their career growth.

Hypotheses

- H0: There is no significant correlation between the acceptance of women marketers across the various dimensions (skillset, socio-cultural barriers, work-life balance, competency, etc.,)

H1: There is a significant correlation between the acceptance of women marketers across the various dimensions (skillset, socio-cultural barriers, work-life balance, competency, etc.,)

- H0: There is no significant correlation between the acceptance of women marketers across the skillsets
H1: There is a significant correlation between the acceptance of women marketers across the skillset
- H0: There is no significant correlation between the acceptance of women marketers across the socio-cultural barriers
H1: There is a significant correlation of the acceptance of women marketers across the socio-cultural barriers
- H0: There is no significant correlation of the acceptance of women marketers across the work-life balance
H1: There is a significant correlation of the acceptance of women marketers across the work-life balance
- H0: There is no significant correlation of the acceptance of women marketers the across competencies
H1: There is a significant correlation of acceptance of women marketers across the competencies

METHODOLOGY

Research Methodology

This research paper and study is limited to Bangalore city. We ascertained that the factors can help to elevate women in the same organisations to grow at the same length and breadth in their career promotions. We assessed the factors that can contribute to the women's career progressions on the basis of skillset, social, cultural barriers, the competitiveness within the organization, work-life balance and how the people perceive of women marketers in the corporate world.

Sampling

- The sample size administered for the study is 210 respondents. The sample size selected is in the ratio 1:5. The data were collected using google forms through a structured questionnaire.
- The nature of the study: The research study was exploratory in nature.

Limitations of the Study

- Individual difference in the people’s perception was a limitation.
- Understanding detrimental stereotypes and conceptions about women and gender equality in corporates was a challenge.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Descriptive statistics is used to break down this information. Descriptive Statistics includes analysing data using frequency distribution, charts like bar graph etc. based on the user’s requirement. In the data analysis section, we have illustrated using certain variables from the questionnaire.

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Reliability Statistics			
Dimension	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
Acceptance	.877	.900	
Skill set	.899		7
Social cultural barriers	.863		6
Competitiveness	.897		9
Work life balance	.898		7

Do you Think Women Marketers Seek Out Challenging Opportunities That Test Her Skills and Abilities?

Table 2: Relationship between Various Variables

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	42	20.0
Disagree	41	19.5
Neither agree nor disagree	42	20.0
Agree	60	28.6
Strongly Agree	25	11.9
Total	210	100.0

Table 2 Women marketers test her skills and abilities

Inference: Around 60% of them agree that women marketers seek for the challenging opportunities that test their skills and abilities, and around 40% of them disagreed. Thus, the majority of them agreed that most of the women marketers seek out challenging opportunities that tests their skills and abilities.

Do the Women Marketers Foresee the Future Trends that Will Influence the Company’s Work?

Table 3: Women Marketers Foresee the Future Trends

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	28	13.3
Disagree	42	20.0
Neither agree nor disagree	48	22.9
Agree	57	27.1
Strongly Agree	35	16.7
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 60% of them agree that women marketers foresee the future trends that will influence the company’s work, around 30% of them disagreed that women marketers foresee the future trends that will influence the company’s work. Thus, the majority of them agreed that women marketers foresee the future trends that will influence the company’s work.

Do Women Marketers Developed Cooperative Relationship among Their Co-Workers?

Table 4: Women Marketers Developed Cooperative Relationship among Her Co-Workers

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	30	14.3
Disagree	39	18.6
Neither agree nor disagree	46	21.9
Agree	51	24.3
Strongly Agree	44	21.0
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 50% of them agree that the women marketers developed a cooperative relationship among their co-workers and around 30% of them disagreed that the women marketers developed cooperative relationship among their co-workers. Thus, the most of them agreed that women marketers developed cooperative relationship among their co-workers.

Do You Think Women Marketers Help People to Progress in their Job by Learning New Skills?

Table 5: Women Marketers Help People to Progress in their Job by Learning News Kills

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	20	9.5
Disagree	46	21.9
Neither agree nor disagree	37	17.6
Agree	59	28.1
Strongly Agree	48	22.9
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 60% of them agree that women marketers help people to progress in their job by learning new skills and around 20% of them disagreed that women marketers help people to progress in their job by learning new skills and around 40% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers help people to progress in their job by learning new skills. We can conclude that the most of the population agreed that women marketers help people to progress in their job

by learning new skills.

Do You Think Women Marketers Follow the Promises and Commitments they Make?

Table 6: Women Marketers Follow the Promises and Commitments they Make

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	24	11.4
Disagree	42	20.0
Neither agree nor disagree	49	23.3
Agree	59	28.1
Strongly Agree	36	17.1
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 60% of them agree that women marketers follow the promises and commitments they make, around 25% of them disagreed that women marketers follow the promises and commitments they make and around 50% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers follow the promises and commitments they make. We can conclude that the most of the population agreed women marketers follow through the promises and commitments they make.

Do You Think Women Marketers are Treated with Same Respect and Dignity as Men?

Table 7: Women Marketers are Treated with Same Respect and Dignity as Men

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	31	14.8
Disagree	63	30.0
Neither agree nor disagree	52	24.8
Agree	37	17.6
Strongly Agree	27	12.9
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 40% of them agree that women marketers are treated with same respect and dignity as men, above 65% of them disagreed that women marketers are treated with same respect and dignity as men and around 55% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers are treated with same respect and dignity as men. We can conclude that the most of the population disagreed that women marketers are treated with same respect and dignity as men.

Do You Think Women Marketers and Men Marketers are Paid Equally?

Table 8: Women Marketers and Men Marketers are Paid Equally

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	41	19.5
Disagree	58	27.6
Neither agree nor disagree	53	25.2
Agree	37	17.6
Strongly Agree	21	10.0
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 40% of them agree that women marketers and men marketers are paid equally, above 60% of them disagreed that women marketers and men marketers are paid equally and around 55% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers and men marketers are paid equally. One can conclude by saying that the most of the population

disagreed that women marketers and men marketers are paid equally.

Do You Think the Social Barriers for Women is Higher than Men?

Table 9: Social Barriers for Women is Higher than Men

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	22	10.5
Disagree	49	23.3
Neither agree nor disagree	39	18.6
Agree	54	25.7
Strongly Agree	46	21.9
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 65% of them agree that the social barriers for women is higher than men, above 50% of them disagreed that the social barriers for women is higher than men and around 40% neither agreed nor disagreed that the social barriers for women is higher than men. Thus, we can tell that the most of them agreed that the social barriers for women are higher that of men.

Do you Think the Ability of Women to Balance Their Work Life Will Affect the Perception of the Indians?

Table 10: Ability of Women to Balance Their Work Life Will Affect the Perception of the Indians

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	31	14.8
Disagree	45	21.4
Neither agree nor disagree	45	21.4
Agree	58	27.6
Strongly Agree	31	14.8
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 70% of them agree that the ability of women to balance their work life will affect the perception of the Indians, above 25% of them disagreed that the ability of women to balance their work life will affect the perception of the Indians and around 40% neither agreed nor disagreed the ability of women to balance their work life will affect the perception of Indians. Thus, we can tell that the most of them agreed that the ability of women to balance their work life will affect the perception of the Indians.

CHI-Square Analysis

Table 11: Relationship between the Variables

Hypothesis	Significance Level	Sig Observed Value	Accepted/Rejected
There is no acceptance of women marketers across various dimensions (skillset, socio-cultural barriers, work-life balance, competency, etc..)	0.05%	0.040	H ₀ is rejected
There is no acceptance of women marketers across the skill sets	0.05%	0.040	H ₀ is rejected
There is no acceptance of women marketers across the social barriers	0.05%	0.041	H ₀ is rejected

Table 11: Contnd.,

There is no acceptance of women marketers across work-life balance.	0.05%	0.006	H ₀ is rejected
There is acceptance of women marketers across competencies.	0.05%	0.033	H ₀ is rejected

Table 11: Correlation Analysis of the Study Dimensions

		Sum of Skill Sets	Sum of Social Barriers	Sum of Competitiveness	Sum of Work Life	Sum of Acceptance
Skill sets	Pearson Correlation	1	.840 **	.838 **	.799 **	.830 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.012
	N	210	210	210	210	210
Social Barriers	Pearson Correlation	.840 **	1	.849 **	.802 **	.824 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.001
	N	210	210	210	210	210
Competitiveness	Pearson Correlation	.838 **	.849 **	1	.825 **	.847 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.014
	N	210	210	210	210	210
Work Life Balance	Pearson Correlation	.799 **	.802 **	.825 **	1	.802 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.024
	N	210	210	210	210	210
Acceptability	Pearson Correlation	.830 **	.824 **	.847 **	.802 **	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.012	.001	.014	.024	
	N	210	210	210	210	210

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) * . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

Research Findings

- Out of the analysed respondents, around 60% of them agree that women marketers seek for challenging opportunities that test their skills and abilities and around 40% of them disagreed
- Out of the analysed respondents, around 60% of them agree that women marketers foresee the future trends that will influence the company's work and around 30% of them disagreed that women marketers foresee the future trends that will influence the company's work
- Around 50% of them agree that the women marketers develop a cooperative relationship among their co-workers and around 30% of them disagreed that the women marketers develop cooperative relationship among their co-workers
- Around 60% of them agree that women marketers follow the promises and commitments they make, around 25% of them disagreed that women marketers follow the promises and commitments they make and around 50% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers follow the promises and commitments they make.
- Around 60% of them agree that women marketers help people to progress in their job by learning new skills and around 20% of them disagreed that women marketers help people to progress in their job by learning new skills and around 40% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers help people grow in their jobs by learning new

skills

- Around 40% of them agree that women marketers are treated with respect and dignity as men, above 65% of them disagreed that women marketers are treated with the same respect and dignity as men and around 55% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers are treated with respect and dignity as men
- According to the people of Bangalore, around 40% of them agree that women marketers and men marketers are paid equally, above 60% of them disagreed that women marketers and men marketers are paid equally and around 55% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers and men marketers are paid equally
- Around 70% of them agree that the ability of women to balance their work life will affect the perception of the Indians, above 25% of them disagreed that the ability of women to balance their work life will affect the perception of the Indians and around 40% neither agreed nor disagreed the ability of women to balance their work life will affect the perception of the Indians

Overall Findings And Suggestions

- Acceptance of women marketers by the people is highly influenced by various dimensions such as a skillset, socio-cultural barriers, work-life balance, competencies etc.
- The correlation of skillset factors with all the four analysed dimensions (i.e. social barriers, competitiveness, work-life balance, acceptance) are found to be positive and significant (at 1% level) indicating that the skillset of the women marketers will aid in acceptance
- Observing the correlation values in the table, shows that the relationship between skillset, competitiveness, work-life balance, social-cultural barriers and acceptance is very high indicating that the social barriers of the women marketers will aid in acceptance
- As per the table, it indicates that the social barriers, work-life balance of the women marketers will aid in acceptance as null hypothesis is rejected
- In Anova, the p value $0.000 < \text{significance value of } 0.05$ and thus we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which in this case is the skillset, social-cultural barriers, competitiveness, work life balance and acceptance are dependent on each other
- Each dimension's co-relational values impact has been analysed against the acceptance and we arrive at competitiveness stands on the top at 0.830 followed by skillset at 0.830, social-cultural barriers at 0.824 and finally with the work life balance at 0.802
- The competitiveness is highly dependent on how the public acceptance on women marketers; we can suggest the organizations can hire more women marketers as it is proved that their skillsets, competitiveness, work life balance and social-cultural barriers are equal with men.
- While formulating an efficient business plan, the companies should design policies and frameworks that could support and empower women to take up greater positions.

- Women Empowerment strategies need to be aligned with the company's requirement and women's abilities and potentialities.
- Companies should encourage constant feedback systems about the work environment and focus on creating a better place to work.
- Organizations should encourage workshops, seminars and training to widen the horizon of men and women employees and groom them to assume higher positions in the organisations.

CONCLUSIONS

As the above research is about the perception of Indians on women marketers, we can conclude by saying that there is a dependency on the skillset a woman marketing personnel possess and the acceptance of her in the corporate world. There is a relationship between how you perceive women in the field of marketing and their skillset and social-cultural barriers they face, the competitiveness in the market for and against the women marketing personnel and the ability of women to balance their work and personal life.

Organizations should encourage their employees to prosper and excel based on their skillset but not on gender basis. All the employees should get equal opportunities to showcase their talent. To make the work environment better, seminars and different events need to be conducted to eliminate the line drawn in the past between male and female working capabilities.

REFERENCES

1. Makova, K. D., & Li, W. H. (2002). Strong male-driven evolution of DNA sequences in humans and apes. *Nature*, 416(6881), 624.
2. Lim, I. S. (1997). Korean immigrant women's challenge to gender inequality at home: The interplay of economic resources, gender, and family. *Gender & society*, 11(1), 31-51.
3. Thompson, L., & Walker, A. J. (1989). Gender in families: Women and men in marriage, work, and parenthood. *Journal of Marriage and the Family*, 845-871.
4. Kabeer, N. (2005). Gender equality and women's empowerment: A critical analysis of the third millennium development goal 1. *Gender & Development*, 13(1), 13-24.
5. Helgesen, S. (1995). *The female advantage: Women's ways of leadership*. Crown Business.
6. Ragins, B. R., Townsend, B., & Mattis, M. (1998). Gender gap in the executive suite: CEOs and female executives report on breaking the glass ceiling. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 12(1), 28-42.
7. Ahlawat, S. S. (1999). *Management programme Women as marketing personnel in Indian perspective*.
8. Phillips, J. (1995). Lending to Women Entrepreneurs. *Com. Lending Rev.*, 11, 65.
9. Fleming-Castaldy, R. P., & Patro, J. (2012). Leadership in occupational therapy: Self-perceptions of occupational therapy managers. *Occupational therapy in health care*, 26(2-3), 187-202.
10. Manning, V., Jones, A., Jones, P., & Fernandez, R. S. (2015). Planning for a smooth transition: evaluation of a succession planning program for prospective nurse unit managers. *Nursing administration quarterly*, 39(1), 58-68.

11. Lee, S. A., Cho, J. E., Park, S., & Lee, S. S. Y. (2013). *It's More Than an M-shape: The Political Economy of Female Non-Standard Workers in the Republic of Korea*. *Asian Social Work and Policy Review*, 7(1), 1-17.
12. Yaseen, Z. (2010). *Leadership styles of men and women in the Arab world*. *Education, Business and Society: Contemporary Middle Eastern Issues*, 3(1), 63-70.
13. Bass, B. M. (1997). *Does the transactional–transformational leadership paradigm transcend organizational and national boundaries?*. *American psychologist*, 52(2), 130.
14. Eagly, A. H., Johannesen-Schmidt, M. C., & Van Engen, M. L. (2003). *Transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire leadership styles: A meta-analysis comparing women and men*. *Psychological bulletin*, 129(4), 569.
15. Ashour, A. S. (1973). *The contingency model of leadership effectiveness: An evaluation*. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 9(3), 339-355.
16. Blumberg, A., & Greenfield, W. (1986). *The effective principal: Perspectives on school leadership*. Publication Sales, Allyn and Bacon, Longwood Division, 7 Wells Avenue, Newton, MA 02159 (Order No. H87406; \$29.95).
17. Sonfield, M. C., & Lussier, R. N. (2004). *First-, second-, and third-generation family firms: A comparison*. *Family Business Review*, 17(3), 189-201.
18. Daughtry, L. H., & Finch, C. R. (1997). *Effective Leadership of Vocational Administrators as a Function of Gender and Leadership Style*. *Journal of Vocational Education Research*, 22(3), 173-86.
19. Druskat, V. U. (1994). *Gender and leadership style: Transformational and transactional leadership in the Roman Catholic Church*. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 5(2), 99-119.
20. Floit, P. S. (1998). *Transformational leadership and the superintendency in Illinois: A comparative study of women and men superintendents*.
21. Foels, R., Driskell, J. E., Mullen, B., & Salas, E. (2000). *The effects of democratic leadership on group member satisfaction: An integration*. *Small Group Research*, 31(6), 676-701.
22. Gabriel, S., & Gardner, W. L. (1999). *Are there "his" and "hers" types of interdependence? The implications of gender differences in collective versus relational interdependence for affect, behavior, and cognition*. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 77(3), 642.
23. Gutek, B. A. (2001). *Women and paid work*. *Psychology of women Quarterly*, 25(4), 379-393.
24. Gutek, B. A., & Morasch, B. (1982). *Sex-ratios, sex-role spillover, and sexual harassment of women at work*. *Journal of Social Issues*, 38(4), 55-74.
25. Hackman, J. R., & Wageman, R. (1995). *Total quality management: Empirical, conceptual, and practical issues*. *Administrative science quarterly*, 309-342.
26. Miller, D. T., Taylor, B., & Buck, M. L. (1991). *Gender gaps: Who needs to be explained?*. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 61(1), 5.
27. Moskowitz, D. S., Suh, E. J., & Desaulniers, J. (1994). *Situational influences on gender differences in agency and communion*. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 66(4), 753.
28. United Nations. Statistical Division. (2000). *The World's Women, 2000: Trends and Statistics (Vol. 16)*. United Nations Publications.

29. *World Health Organization (2002). "Gender and Reproductive Rights: Working Definitions". Retrieved 15 November 2012.*
30. *Jayapalan (2001). Indian society and social institutions. Atlantic Publishers &Distri. p. 145. ISBN 978-81-7156-925-0.*
31. *National Resource Center for Women. "Women in History". Archived from the original on 2009-06-19. Retrieved 24 December 2006*
32. *Mahajan P. T., Golahit S. B. Engineering a Woman: Marketing Opportunities and Challenges in India. American Journal of Management Science and Engineering. Vol. 2, No. 1, 2017, pp. 11-22. doi: 10.11648/j.ajmse.20170201.12*
33. *MacKinnon, C. A. (1987). Feminism unmodified: Discourses on life and law. Harvard university press.*